

Cyclodehydration of ω -Aryloxyacetophenones by Polyphosphoric Acid: Part II. Synthesis of Aryl Substituted Benzofurans

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p-Methoxyphenacyl-phenyl, *p*-methoxyphenacyl-*p*'-methyl phenyl, *p*-methoxyphenacyl-*p*'-methoxy phenyl and *p*-methoxy phenacyl-*o*-methoxy phenyl ethers (I to IV) have been synthesised by treating *p*-methoxy phenacyl bromide with the corresponding phenols. The ethers were then subjected to aromatic cyclodehydration by PPA to afford 2-(*p*-methoxy phenyl) benzofurans (V-VIII).

In part I¹, the synthesis of some 2-phenyl and 3-phenylbenzofurans have been described. In the present communication, we report the synthesis of some 2-(*p*-methoxy phenyl) benzofurans obtained by the cyclodehydration of ω -aryloxyacetophenones with polyphosphoric acid. To achieve this, the following aryloxyacetophenones have been prepared by refluxing *p*-methoxy phenacyl bromide with the corresponding phenols in dry acetone in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate.

- (I) $R = R' = R'' = H$
 (II) $R = R' = H$; $R'' = -CH_3$
 (III) $R = R' = H$; $R'' = -OCH_3$
 (IV) $R = -OCH_3$; $R' = R'' = H$.

The aryloxyacetophenones thus obtained have been subjected to aromatic cyclodehydration by polyphosphoric acid at different temperatures.

1. K. K. Thomas and M. M. Bokadia, *This Journal*, 1966, **43**, 713.

- (V) $R = R' = R'' = H$
 (VI) $R = R' = H; R'' = CH_3$
 (VII) $R = R' = H; R'' = OCH_3$
 (VIII) $R = OCH_3, R' = R'' = H$

Unlike the earlier observation it has been found that the introduction of a methoxy group in the para position of the ring B, greatly facilitates the process of cyclodehydration and the rearrangement of 3-aryl- to 2-aryl isomer. Indeed in this series, even at lower temperatures, the rearranged product i.e. 2-aryl benzofuran was obtained and in no case the 3-aryl benzofuran could be isolated. Moreover, it has been observed that considerable amount of charring and polymerisation occurs especially at higher temperatures.

Thus the cyclodehydration of *w*-phenoxy-4-methoxy acetophenone with P.P.A. yielded the best yield (70%) of 2-*p*-methoxy phenyl benzofuran (V) at 60° and the 3-aryl isomer was not obtained in this case. 2-*p*-Methoxy phenyl benzofuran was obtained previously by the lead tetra-acetate oxidation of 4'-methoxy flavan-3, 4-diol (IX) followed by acid treatment of the product thus obtained².

Thus the 2-*p*-methoxy phenyl benzofuran (V) obtained by the aromatic cyclodehydration is completely identical with this product. The U.V. spectra of 2-phenyl benzofuran and 2-*p*-methoxy benzofuran have been recorded. The introduction of a methoxy group in the *p*-position has effected a bathochromic shift of U. V. absorption band.

EXPERIMENTAL

ω-Phenoxy-4-methoxy acetophenone or *p* methoxy phenacylphenyl ether. (I)

p-Methoxy phenacyl bromide (23 g.) prepared by Friedel-Craft's reaction of anisole and bromoacetyl bromide³ was refluxed with phenol (9.4 g.) in the presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (13.8 g.) in dry acetone (50 ml) for about 4 hrs. The reaction mixture was cooled and then poured in water and chilled. The resulting solid was filtered, dried and crystallised from rectified spirit as colourless crystals (m.p. 66-67°; yield, 17 g.). Literature³ records m.p. 83-84°. (Found C, 74.6; H, 5.71; calculated for C₁₅H₁₄O₃; C, 74.4.; H, 5.78%).

ω-(4-Methyl phenoxy)-4'-methoxy acetophenone or *p*-methoxy phenacyl-*p*'-methyl phenyl ether (II).

p-Methoxy phenacyl bromide (23 g.) and *p*-cresol (10.8 g.) were refluxed with potassium carbonate (13.8 g.) in dry acetone (50 ml.) and worked up in the usual manner to yield a solid product (18.5 g.) which was recrystallised from ethanol as colourless crystals, m.p. 83-84°. (Found: C, 75.0; H, 5.9; C₁₆H₁₆O₃ requires C, 75.0; H, 6.2%).

ω-(4-methoxy-phenoxy)-4'-methoxy acetophenone or *p*-methoxy phenacyl-*p*'-methoxy phenyl ether (III).

It was prepared in the usual manner from *p*-methoxy phenacyl bromide (23 g.) and hydroquinone monomethyl ether (12.4 g.). The reaction product was crystallised from rectified spirit as colourless needles (m.p. 72-73°; yield 20 g.) (Found C, 71.2; H, 5.85; C₂₆H₁₆O₄ requires C, 70.6; H, 5.88%).

ω-(2-Methoxy-phenoxy) 4'-methoxy acetophenone or *p*-methoxy phenacyl-*o*'-methoxy phenyl ether (IV).

It was prepared in the usual manner from guaiacol and *p*-methoxy phenacyl bromide in 55% yield. It was recrystallised from ethyl alcohol as colourless crystals. m.p. 82-83°. (Found C, 71.1; H, 5.92; C₁₆H₁₆O₄ requires, C, 70.6; H, 5.88%).

(1) Cyclodehydration of *ω*-phenoxy-4-methoxy acetophenone (synthesis of 2-*p*-methoxy phenyl benzofuran) (V).

(a) At temperature 132°. Polyphosphoric acid prepared from P₂O₅ (42 g.) and phosphoric acid (20 ml.) was heated at 132° for about 20 minutes and then the aryloxyacetophenone (5 g.) was added. It was then heated at 132° for 2 hrs. with occasional stirring. After cooling, it was poured in water and steam distilled. The product (1.8 g.) was then recrystallised from rectified spirit as colourless flakes. m.p. 151°. lit² m.p. 152°. (Found C, 79.8; H, 5.4; calculated for C₁₅H₁₂O₂, C, 80.35; H, 5.35%).

It gave a 2,4, 7-trinitrofluorenone derivative which crystallised as amber coloured needles from absolute alcohol-benzene mixture, m.p. 150-151°. (Found N, 7.7; C₂₈H₁₇N₃O₃ requires N, 7.8%).

3. F. Krochnke, G. Krochnke and G. W. Arenholz, *J. Prak. Chem.*, 1950, **11**, 239-48; C. A. **56**, 15407, 1962.

4. R. Stoermes and P. A. Tenstädt, *Ber.*, 1902, **35**, 3565.

(b) *Cyclodehydration at 80°*. Cyclodehydration of the aryloxyacetophenone (5 g) at 80° for about 3½ hr. was tried. The product on dilution and steam distillation was identified as 2-(*p*-methoxy phenyl)-benzofuran from its m.p. and mixed m.p. 151°; yield 2.5 g.

(c) *Cyclodehydration at 60°*. Cyclodehydration (5 g.) was carried out at 60° for about 3½ hr. The same product with better yield (3.2 g.) was obtained.
(m.p. 151°, mixed m.p. 150-151°).

(d) *At room temperature*. Cyclodehydration did not take place at room temperature even on keeping the mixture for about 24 hr.

(2) *Cyclodehydration of ω-(4-methyl-phenoxy)-4'-methoxy Acetophenone (II) (2-p-methoxyphenyl-5-methyl benzofuran) (VI)*.

(a) The cyclodehydration of the aryl oxyacetophenone(II) (5 g.) at 132° was carried out for 2 hr. and after dilution the product steam distilled. The steam distilled product recrystallised from alcohol as colourless flakes, m.p. 172°; yield 1.5 g. (Found, C, 79.9; H, 5.90; C₁₆H₁₄O₂ requires C, 80.7; H, 5.88%).

Its 2, 4, 7-trinitrofluorenone derivative was crystallised from absolute alcohol as violet brown needles, m.p. 142-143°.

A large amount of material mostly charred was left in the flask. An attempt was made to extract the benzofuran with ether, but only traces could be obtained.

(b) *At 80°*. Cyclodehydration at 80° for about 3½ hr. followed by steam distillation gave the same benzofuran with 50% yield, m.p. 172, mixed m.p. 172°.

The flask however contained a large amount of uncharred substance. It was filtered and dissolved in ether. The ether extract on repeated crystallisation from alcohol and decolourisation with animal charcoal gave about 0.5 g. of the benzofuran. However, most of the residue seems to be a polymerised product.

(c) *At 60°*. Cyclodehydration at 60° for about 4 hr. gave only traces of a product which could not be characterised.

(3) *Cyclodehydration of ω-(4-methoxy phenoxy)-4'-methoxy acetophenone(III) (2-p-methoxy-phenyl-5-methoxy benzofuran) (VII)*.

(a) *At 132°*. Aryloxyacetophenone(II) (5 g.) was dehydrated at 132° for 2 hr. Considerable charring occurred and steam distillation of the product gave only small amount of the benzofuran which was crystallised from rectified spirit, m.p. 163°.

(b) *At 80°*. Cyclodehydration of the aryloxyacetophenone (5 g.) at 80° for 3 hr. followed by steam distillation gave about 0.5 g. of the benzofuran which was crystallised from rectified spirit., m.p. and mixed m.p. with the above same, 163°.

The uncharred substance left in the flask was extracted with ether and repeated crystallisation and decolourisation yielded a small quantity of the benzofuran. Most of the residue also seems to be polymerised product.

(4) *Attempted cyclodehydration of (2-methoxy-phenoxy)-4'-methoxy acetophenone(IV).*

Cyclodehydration at 132° and 80° were attempted. The product could not be isolated by steam distillation. Extraction with ether and subsequent attempt to purify yielded only an intractable mass.

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